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Surgical Correction and Postoperative Management Strategy in “Apple Peel” (Pagoda) Syndrome

INTRODUCTION

Among congenital anomalies presenting with intestinal obstruction, various types of small intestinal atresia represent a distinct group: membranous atresia, single atresia, atresia with a defect of the intestinal wall, multiple atresias, and atresias with interruption of the mesentery and intestinal tube.

All of these defects require surgical treatment.

The most technically challenging anomaly for surgical correction is “apple peel” (pagoda) syndrome, characterized not only by an extensive defect of the intestinal tube but also by a large mesenteric defect of the small intestine with absence of a segment of the superior mesenteric artery (*a. mesenterica superior*) and spiral twisting of the distal small bowel around a narrow mesentery. Blood supply is maintained through collateral vascular arcades between the middle colic artery (*a. colica media*) or right colic artery (*a. colica dextra*) and the terminal branch of the ileocolic artery (*a. ileocolica*).

“Apple peel” syndrome is relatively rare in clinical practice, occurring in approximately 1:250,000 newborns (Paterson-Brown, 1991) or in about 5% of all cases of small bowel atresia (Smith, 1989). Mortality remains high, ranging from 45% to 63.4%.

The extent and nature of the surgical procedure remain controversial, including the optimal level of resection of the proximal and distal segments, the type of intestinal anastomosis, and the method for closing the mesenteric defect. In 50% of cases, this defect is associated with incomplete intestinal rotation. However, the literature lacks clear descriptions of operative management in such combined cases.

An important consideration is that the organs and tissues of the newborn are still undergoing active growth. The distal bowel segment at birth is hypoplastic and, in this anomaly, has compromised trophic supply. This leads to persistent postoperative motor-evacuatory and absorptive-secretory dysfunction. Morphostructural changes in distal bowel segments have not

been well described in the literature. These factors underscore the clinical relevance of this condition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Between 2002 and 2012, seven newborns underwent surgery for “apple peel” syndrome, accounting for 5.7% of all patients treated for small bowel atresia.

In three patients, the syndrome was combined with incomplete intestinal rotation (stage I); in two patients, it was associated with volvulus of the proximal atretic segment; in one patient, with multiple distal atresias without mesenteric interruption.

One infant was admitted one month later for repeat reconstructive surgery due to intestinal obstruction. In addition to anastomotic stenosis, persistent “apple peel” syndrome combined with incomplete intestinal rotation (stage I) was identified.

Gestational age ranged from 34 to 39 weeks, and birth weight ranged from 2600 to 3200 g.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In two cases, prenatal diagnosis incorrectly suggested duodenal atresia; postnatally, jejunal atresia was confirmed. In the remaining cases, diagnosis was established within 2–18 hours after birth.

Diagnosis was confirmed by plain abdominal radiography and contrast enema studies. Characteristic radiographic findings included 3–4 broad horizontal air-fluid levels in the epigastric and mesogastric regions and absence of distal bowel gas. Contrast enema revealed microcolon in all cases; in three patients, a left-sided colon configuration resembling a “double-barrel” pattern was observed.

The length of the proximal atretic jejunal segment ranged from 15 to 40 cm. The dilated segment measured 8–15 cm in length, with maximal diameter up to 7 cm.

All patients had extensive mesenteric defects. The distal bowel segment was twisted in a spiral configuration around a narrow mesentery. The sole arterial supply was the ileocolic artery (*a. ileocolica*). A correlation was noted: the longer the distal segment, the poorer the blood supply to its proximal portion, occasionally progressing to necrosis.

SURGICAL MANAGEMENT

Surgical treatment consisted of:

- Resection of the dilated and partially hypertrophied proximal segment

- Untwisting of the spiral distal ileum
- Assessment of distal bowel viability
- Resection of nonviable segments
- End-to-end enteroenteric anastomosis
- Closure of the mesenteric defect

In two cases, longitudinal resection of the hypertrophied proximal segment was performed to equalize the diameters of the anastomosed bowel ends.

In three patients, incomplete intestinal rotation was corrected after creation of the intestinal anastomosis.

Routine evaluation of the remaining distal bowel for internal membranes was performed. In one infant with multiple internal membranes, bowel-preserving enterotomy with excision of three membranes was performed, followed by anastomosis involving two-thirds of the lumen; a total of four anastomoses were created in this patient.

Postoperative small bowel length measured 50 cm in two patients and 80 cm in five patients.

POSTOPERATIVE COURSE

A characteristic feature of postoperative management was prolonged absence of motor-evacuatory gastrointestinal function, manifested by persistent stasis and delayed spontaneous bowel movements.

Parenteral nutrition was required until restoration of gastrointestinal transit. In recent years, an intraoperative transanastomotic tube has been placed to facilitate earlier initiation of enteral feeding.

On average, gastrointestinal function recovered within 1–1.5 months postoperatively.

Radiographic contrast studies were performed at 3–4 weeks postoperatively (images at 4, 12, 24, and 48 hours) to assess transit.

HISTOLOGICAL FINDINGS

Histological examination revealed focal mucosal atrophy and uneven muscular hypertrophy with absence of ganglion cells in the dilated segment.

The distal segment demonstrated mucosal hyperplasia, muscular hypoplasia, and sparse, unevenly distributed ganglion cells.

OUTCOMES

Six patients survived. Mean hospitalization ranged from 50 to 97 days.

Two patients (with residual bowel length ≤ 50 cm) required treatment for short bowel syndrome for up to 6 months.

One infant died on day 42 of life due to nosocomial sepsis.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Among various forms of small bowel atresia, “apple peel” syndrome represents the most surgically challenging variant.
 2. Resection of the dilated, sac-like, partially hypertrophied proximal segment is mandatory.
 3. Significant shortening of the small intestine leads to short bowel syndrome.
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